

Haptic Rendering for Gaussian Splatting with Implicit Surfaces

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Abstract. This paper presents a haptic rendering method for 3D Gaussian Splatting (GS) based on implicit surface formulations. While GS represents scenes using Gaussians, it does not explicitly define surfaces, which limits its direct use for haptic interaction. To address this, we construct implicit scalar fields from GS and integrate them into a constraint-based haptic rendering framework. Two formulations are considered: a Gaussian summation field and a Log-Sum-Exp (LSE) formulation based on ellipsoidal primitives. Although the LSE approach involves a trade-off between stability and geometric accuracy, it provided more stable and consistent rendering than the Gaussian summation formulation.

Keywords: Haptic rendering · Gaussian Splatting · Collision detection.

1 Introduction

3D Gaussian Splatting (GS) [1] has attracted attention in the graphics community due to its ability to reconstruct high-quality 3D scenes from images and its flexibility for editing based on a simple representation as a set of Gaussians. These properties make GS a promising representation for haptic applications, such as surgical simulation. However, haptic rendering with GS remains challenging because it does not explicitly define object surfaces. A common solution is to extract polygonal surfaces (e.g., using [4]) as a preprocessing step, which introduces additional computational cost and implementation complexity. Alternatively, Gaussians can be interpreted as an implicit representation of surfaces, but they are optimized for visualization and do not always yield well-defined surfaces for haptic interaction. In this paper, we propose a method for stable haptic rendering of GS based on implicit surface formulations. Our goal is to generate consistent force feedback without vibration or unintended penetration.

2 Method

We employ a constraint-based haptic rendering method for implicit surfaces [3]. The object surface is defined by an implicit function $S(x)$, where the zero level

Fig. 1: 2D examples of isosurfaces (yellow lines) generated by Gaussian sum and Log-Sum-Exp (LSE) with same three Gaussians.

set $S(x) = 0$ represents the surface. The gradient $\nabla S(x)$ is used to compute the contact point from the haptic device position. To construct $S(x)$ from GS, we consider two approaches. The first is a Gaussian-based formulation. In this formulation, a scene is represented as a set of anisotropic Gaussians. The i -th Gaussian is expressed as

$$G_i(x) = \alpha_i \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(x - \mu_i)^\top \Sigma_i^{-1}(x - \mu_i)\right), \quad (1)$$

where α_i , μ_i , and Σ_i denote opacity, mean, and covariance, respectively. A simple implicit surface can be defined by summing the Gaussians:

$$S_{\text{GS}}(x) = \sum_i G_i(x) - \tau, \quad (2)$$

where τ is a threshold parameter controlling the surface offset. An example of the resulting isosurface is shown in Fig. 1a. The second approach is a Log-Sum-Exp (LSE) formulation, which has been used to represent smooth implicit surfaces from multiple primitives in applications such as physics simulation [2]. Each Gaussian induces a quadratic function

$$v_i(x) = (x - \mu_i)^\top \Sigma_i^{-1}(x - \mu_i), \quad (3)$$

whose level sets form ellipsoids centered at μ_i . Using the LSE function, the scalar field is defined as

$$S_{\text{LSE}}(x) = -\frac{1}{k} \log\left(\sum_i \alpha_i \exp(-k v_i(x))\right) - \tau, \quad (4)$$

where k controls the smoothness of the field and τ is a threshold defining the isosurface. Larger values of k approximate a hard minimum over the set of quadratic functions. Examples of the resulting isosurfaces are shown in Fig. 1b and Fig. 1c. Note that the gradient expressions are analytically derived.

3 Preliminary Evaluation

We implemented the proposed method and conducted a preliminary evaluation. The system was implemented on a Windows PC equipped with an Intel Core

Fig. 2: Proxy (contact point) trajectories under Gaussian sum and LSE conditions. Red and blue lines indicate contact and non-contact states, respectively; trajectories start near the upper left and are shown without GS occlusion.

i7-9700K CPU (3.7–4.9 GHz). Haptic computations were executed on a single thread. A Phantom Premium 1.5 HF (3D Systems, Inc.) was used as the force feedback device. As a target object, we created a simple scene including a desk and a plate using Scaniverse (Niantic). The scene consists of approximately 23k Gaussians. The feedback force stiffness parameter was set to 1000 N/m.

A participant was asked to push and slide on the plate under both conditions. The proxy (contact point) trajectories driven by the haptic device are shown in Fig. 2. Both methods achieved real-time performance at approximately 1 kHz, with most time steps computed in less than 1 ms. In the Gaussian summation condition, the force feedback exhibited small vibrations, and penetration through the surface occasionally occurred. The vibration is likely related to the limit cycle behavior [3], which can arise when interacting with concave regions. Penetration may be caused by small gaps in the implicit volume. Increasing τ reduces these issues by inflating the surface, but this leads to poor alignment with the visual geometry. In contrast, the LSE formulation showed more stable behavior, likely due to its smoother surface representation. Penetration was avoided by setting a sufficiently large value of τ , which effectively inflates the surface. However, this introduces a trade-off between surface detail preservation and stability. Further investigation is required to achieve more accurate force rendering.

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

The proposed method enables stable haptic rendering for Gaussian splatting; however, the surface representation tends to be inflated and loses fine geometric details. Improving the accuracy of surface representation while maintaining stability remains an open problem. We invite discussion on more precise implicit surface formulations, efficient algorithms for real-time evaluation, and approaches to optimize GS representations for haptic interaction.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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